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Action Research

**The Study of the Effects of Learning English in Sleep on Ninth-
Grade Students of Sadra 2 High School for Girls**

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Abstract

The present study aimed to determine the effectiveness of learning English in sleep in ninth-grade students studying at Sadra 2 High School for Girls in Tabriz. All first-year high school students, 15 of whom were selected as a sample applying the targeted sampling method, constituted the statistical population of the present research. In this study, using a tape recorder, 60 irregular verbs and 15 phrases from the ninth grade English course, lesson 6, along with their Persian equivalents, recorded on a tape, were played continuously for 90 minutes. The next day, the students were tested and based on the results of this test, the average number of correctly detected words indicated that from among the 60 irregular verbs, the highest number of identified verbs was equal to 10, and, from among the 15 phrases, only four phrases were recognized correctly. In total, after 8 sessions of experimenting, students managed to identify 30 verbs and 10 phrases precisely. Overall, the findings of the present investigation confirmed the hypothesis that learning can happen during sleep, and according to the agreement made with the parents of the students, this test could be done in a psychology lab or at home.

Keywords: *learning English, sleep, ninth-grade high school students*

Introduction

Learning is one of the important psychological processes. Many interventions have been made to strengthen students' learning levels. Over the years of research, researchers have come up with the question that since learning is a natural process, is there a natural mechanism to support it or not? (Kapsi et al., 2020).

A human spends one-third of his/her lifetime in sleep. Sleep is the only very effective process for re-regulating the daily health of the brain and body, and therefore, is very important and essential for human health (Besedovsky et al., 2019).

Sleep is considered a basic process for the brain and cognition to function. It is a state of consciousness in which most of the senses are put aside, disabled and inactive, followed by a lack of responsiveness to the environment. While the body remains motionless and visual contact is lost, the response to the sound is broadcast. Short-term memory stops transferring information to long-term memory and this path is closed. (Carskadon & Dement, 2011).

Although learning in sleep is human's long-standing dream, research has shown that you cannot consciously learn anything in your sleep. However, the lack of consciousness does not rule out the possibility that we can perceive and store the events unconsciously. In fact, if sleep was associated with a complete shutdown of the brain, our chances of survival would be lost because no noise would be felt at night to wake us up immediately (Ruch & Henke, 2020).

In a study, Van Der Donckt et al. (2022) argued that deep learning can be achieved while sleeping. Neumann et al. (2020) found that perfume can help optimize learning in sleep.

The current research aims to examine whether learning English while asleep is effective for ninth-grade students studying at Sadra 2 High School for girls.

Theoretical Foundations of the Research

Sleep is a physiological state that varies in different brain function cycles. In fact, the brain undergoes several periods of metabolic and neurological changes which distinguish sleep from arousal (Walker & Stickgold, 2006).

Sleep is associated with the basic physiological functions of the body, i.e., hormones, body temperature regulation, immune system, tissue regeneration and ontogenesis. Sleep deprivation can result in an increase in blood pressure, glucose tolerance, insulin sensitivity, and diabetes. It also causes growth, cognitive, and emotional disorders (Perogamvros et al., 2013).

Research Methodology

All first-year high school female students, 15 of whom were selected as a sample applying the targeted sampling method, constituted the statistical population of the present research.

Using a tape recorder, 60 irregular verbs and 15 phrases from the ninth grade English course, lesson 6, along with their Persian equivalents, recorded on a tape, were played continuously for 90 minutes.

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Each of the 15 subjects was expected to go to bed at 10:30 p.m. Around 12:00 a.m., the test assistant, the student's mother, made sure that the student was asleep. When the subject fell asleep, she inserted the tape, on which 60 irregular verbs and 15 phrases from lesson 6, along with their Persian equivalents, were recorded, into the tape recorder and turned it on. These words and phrases were played continuously for 90 minutes. The recording should be played when the student was asleep, otherwise, the test assistant turned off the recording until the subject fell asleep again and she could turn the recording back on. To detect the number of correctly identified items by the subject, the next morning, the same recorded tape was played for her and she was asked to listen to each word or phrase in English and say its Persian equivalent.

The Results

Based on the results of the above test, the average number of correctly detected words indicated that from among the 60 irregular verbs, the highest number of identified verbs was equal to 10, and, from among the 15 phrases, only four phrases were recognized correctly. In total, after 8 sessions of experimenting, students managed to identify 30 verbs and 10 phrases precisely.

Discussion

Overall, the findings of the present investigation confirmed the hypothesis that learning can happen during sleep, and according to the agreement made with the parents of the students, this test could be done in a psychology lab or at home.

The findings of the present study are in line with the results of Neumann et al. (2020). It should be noted that in the current research, to conduct the test, a control group was also considered, and it seems that this experiment is an effective and motivating method for students who are not interested in learning English. Of course, the cooperation between the teacher, students, students' parents and the vice-chancellor of the school made a significant contribution to the success of the experiment. Also, it is worth noticing that a tape recorder or a simple phone, which is available to everyone, was the only tool utilized to record and listen to recordings.

Research Limitations

Since the statistical sample of the present study was limited to ninth-grade high school female students, care should be taken in generalizing the results to male students as well as students studying at other educational levels.

Suggestions

The researcher, as an English teacher and a Ph.D. in educational psychology, suggests that this experiment should be utilized creatively as a diverse method in learning other subjects.

Moreover, similar research should be conducted on male students and their learning results should be compared with female students.

Teachers in in-service courses and teacher training centers should familiarize themselves with such interventional research methods so that they can apply similar methods to raise the learning level of all their students.

The experience and knowledge of educational psychologists should be employed at all educational levels to improve students' learning levels and familiarize teachers with various teaching methods and aids in all courses.

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